

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

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DISTINCTIONS BETWEEN TRADITIONAL AND MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract. *The purpose of this study is to determine the differences between the historical and modern education systems. The comparison method was mainly used to determine the differences. It discusses how history education can limit students' critical thinking and creativity. The historical education system usually includes a teacher-centered approach, where students receive education passively through lectures, textbooks, and exams. As you read the research, you can clearly see this in the "Gurukul" teaching system, which is one of the historical educational systems. However, in recent years, student-centered learning has supplanted the historical education system and there has been a shift to a more modern education system that emphasizes the use of technology to enhance the learning experience. Overall, the research provides insight into the benefits of transitioning from an older education system to an approach that better prepares students for the challenges of 21st century life.*

Key words: *old education, modern education, "Gurukul" system.*

Introduction

"Education is not a preparation for life; education is life itself."

John Dewey

Now in the rapidly developing world, everything is being updated and developed. In particular, the education has also changed, as the years pass, there have been quite significant changes. New education systems, new methods, new technologies and new information. We witness a great difference when we compare the old education system with the modern one.

The historical education system was mainly aimed at philosophical world and was a key goal of delivering the morality, values and social skills necessary for survival of future generations. Students were taught by religious leaders and scholars. There was no specific space for the educational process, the education of the learning scholars, and established in various gardens. The lessons were mainly conducted in the form of lectures and a story, and students studied their lessons listening to their teachers. Students are disciples with their teachers and became the successors of the scribes. In this order, the historical system continued as a teacher and student.

In the modern education system, the scientific world is a priority and the education is flexible to the changing world. Currently, students are lessons from education in special educational institutions, qualified teachers and professors.

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According to students' abilities in modern education, teachers can adapt them and students in their direction. The textbooks are specialized for each direction, which can be mastered in different forms. And at the same time, students are gradually learned from young people for future professions and prepared for future lives. Modern education is more interesting and intensive for students using various computer technologies, internet and projectors. Modern education reduces the limitations of the historical system to study through practice and experience, unlike traditional textbooks and theoretical learning.

Let us consider one of the historical education systems, 'Gurukul', a traditional method of teaching that has been used for centuries in India.

"Gurukul" is a school where teacher and student live together and study in residential conditions. This education was established around 5000 BC in what is now the Indian state of Uttar Pradesh. There, the students moved to their teacher's house and lived there until the end of their studies. Students living in gurukul were away from home for months to years. The Gurukul system of education was a system that provided students with a variety of educational and vocational experiences, where students studied Vedic literature, Sanskrit, mathematics, and other traditional Indian subjects, as well as arts, sports, and handicrafts. In addition to scientific knowledge, students learned such qualities as self-discipline, politeness, humanity, and spirituality through Gurukul. It was also mandatory to do daily tasks independently. Students from the Gurukul have grown into enlightened people.

All students studied the same curriculum and the same lessons. It was believed that this would help students learn in a comfortable environment and not be judged based on their background. No tuition fees were charged because the relationship between teacher and student was considered very sacred. At the end of the education, before the students leave the educational establishment, the traditional gesture of 'guru dakshina', a gesture of respect and gratitude to the educational establishment, is given.

But at the same time, this educational system also had its own shortcomings:

- women were not admitted to the gurukul;
- students were away from the outside world because they lived in the gurukul;
- they have not faced the harsh realities of life;
- students were away from their parents and homes;
- were obliged to follow the guru whether he was right or wrong.

Over time, Gurukul system was replaced by new modern education systems and the concept of Gurukul education disappeared. When Indians compare Gurukul

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education and modern education, they point out that the personality development and moral education present in gurukul are absent in modern education. But they also admit that both education systems have enough flaws.`

Body part

In today's era of increased emphasis on science and technology, the modern education system is widely used in educational institutions and is significantly different from the historical education system. Let us witness these differences by comparing a few.

1. Education system:

Historical education system focuses more on theory. Students learned by reading and hearing, so this type of learning was passive and limited, which led to a loss of enthusiasm in the classroom. Education focused on the memorization of facts rather than personal growth and creativity of students. And a strict curriculum was established for education, and all students were required to study this curriculum.

- modern education system is comprehensive. In this educational system, various methods have been developed considering the needs of the students. This brought variety to education and increased passion for learning. For the proper growth and development of students, a step-by-step education tailored to their youth has been created. This ensured that the student received maximum knowledge suitable for his age. And again, in modern education, much attention was paid to the personal development of students, abandoning the historical education system. It emphasized skills such as critical thinking, creativity, communication and problem solving.

2. Educational methods:

The historical education system was teacher-oriented. The main role was played by the teacher and the only source of knowledge was the teacher. Students were passive in the learning process and always listened to the teacher's lectures. Teachers were responsible for delivering information, lectures, textbooks, and other learning materials to students. In this, students had to follow the instructions of their teachers and thus maintain order and discipline. Students listening and memorizing the teacher's information was considered the main method of the historical education system.

In some respects, this educational system seemed orderly and disciplined compared to today's, but the structured curriculum limited student activity and personal development.

In the modern education system, the teacher has changed to a guide for the student. Teachers are now embodied as a guide, supporter and environment creator

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for students. Students not only rely on their teachers, but also expand their knowledge by exchanging ideas and collaborating with other group members. It also involves students learning from each other and solving problems together. A student who learns through cooperation develops the skills of listening, empathy, and compromise on their own. This is a great help to the student in their future success, because they will develop the skills to work effectively in cooperation, support each other, and resolve disagreements. Thus, we can recognize modern education as a student-centered approach.

3. Technology:

During the historical education system, technology did not yet exist. Educational processes were carried out through books. If we consider education as a book, a teacher and a student, it has hardened as a certain shell. Nevertheless, the students made good use of this book, which is a source of knowledge, and increased their knowledge.

- technology has introduced a large amount of information systems into today's education. This in itself gave the students the opportunity to study in the field of their choice. Various educational platforms, applications and online resources have been developed for education. At the same time, technology has brought educational games, multimedia presentations and video resources to make lessons more interesting. This gave students more motivation to learn. With the introduction of technology in education, students have the opportunity to study remotely from anywhere.

At the same time, I would like to mention that as much as technology has brought convenience to students, it has also brought laziness, distraction and inactivity. Appropriate use of digital technologies has become a personal choice of the student.

4. Evaluation:

In the historical education system, the assessment method was usually conducted in the form of tests, essays and exams. When a student is graded, he is given no feedback, no information on areas to improve, just numbers or letters.

- in the modern education system, evaluation through tests and exams is still preserved, but not limited to these methods, the new evaluation system is based on the student's thinking. This includes assessment with a variety of demonstrations. Currently, assessment through assignments, projects and presentations that students have prepared themselves is popular. This assessment method not only develops the student's theoretical knowledge but also practical skills through experience.

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5. Class:

Class has played an important role in the historical education system. The system was notable for its inequality. Representatives of the upper class received quality education, they had access to special schools, private tutors and various extracurricular activities. The lower classes, on the other hand, are limited in opportunities because they do not have enough money.

Even with the modern education system, stratification has not completely disappeared. Also, a certain part of the population does not have the opportunity to get an education due to insufficient funds. But when we compare it with the historical system, the differentiation is much reduced by now. Various curricula have been developed to educate the people in equality and these programs prevent segregation.

6. Gender:

In the historical education system, educational opportunities could be clearly divided according to gender. In this educational system, girls had limited opportunities for education and career advancement compared to boys. Girls were responsible for domestic or caring roles. Even if women studied, this situation was not accepted by the society and led to various discriminations.

- Today, there is an increasing focus on ensuring equality in the field of education, supporting educational opportunities for all students, regardless of gender identity. Today we can see that historical views are disappearing with time and women have equal opportunities.

Conclusion

Although there are differences between the historical and modern education systems, it is important to note that despite our modern achievements, we are currently improving the efficiency of the current system by integrating outdated methods. Each form of education has its own role and importance. Both these educational systems had their advantages in their time.

Overall, the transition from the old education system to the modern education system has been equally fair, supportive, quality and safe for all. Thus, the modern education system strives to prepare students for a rapidly changing world.

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